

The logo for Campus Europae features a stylized letter 'E' composed of three vertical bars. The leftmost bar is dark grey, the middle bar is orange, and the rightmost bar is dark grey.

Campus **E**uropae

A laboratory for Mobility

February 2013

INDEX

Foreword - p. 6

Prof. Antonio Ferrari, President of EUF-CE

The contribution of Campus Europae to the European Higher Education Area - p. 10

Prof. Noel Whelan, first President EUF-CE 2003 - 2007

Why Europe needs Campus Europae - p. 13

Erna Hennicot-Schoepges, Luxembourg Minister of Higher Education and Research 1999 - 2004

The great challenge: educating a new generation of Europeans - p. 16

Dr. Konrad Schily, initiator of Campus Europae

Keeping the social dimension alive - p. 20

Achim Meyer auf der Heyde, Vice-President of the European Council for Student Affairs

Campus Europae, a source of new ideas - p. 23

Doris Pack, Member of the European Parliament since 1989

Towards 99% of Academic Recognition - p. 26

Prof. Estela Pereira, CE Ombudsperson

A student centred network - p. 30

Katharina Miller, President of the EUF-CE Student Council 2003 - 2005

Ride for Your Rights! - p. 33

Julian Walkowiak, President of the EUF-CE Student Council 2010 - 2012

Language learning to understand the Cultural unity in diversity - p. 37

Prof. Wilfried Hartmann, Chair of the Teacher Training Subject Committee since 2003

Bologna meets Lisbon - p. 49

Birgit Brödermann, Intercultural Consulant and Project Coordinator, Arbeit und Leben Hamburg

Tearing down borders in Higher Education - p. 52

Fuada Stankovic, Rector of the University of Novi Sad 2001 - 2004

Human Rights and Higher Education - p. 56

Sjur Bergan, Head of the Education Department of the Council of Europe

On the way to the 20th anniversary of Campus Europae - p. 60

François Biltgen, Minister for Higher Education and Research - Luxembourg

History - p. 62

Prof. Christoph Ehmann, Secretary-General of EUF-CE since 2003

References - p. 66

Prof. Ferrari

President EUF-CE

"The affinities between CE and Bologna are not just in timing but, far more important, in a shared vision of the construction of a European Higher Education Area"

Foreword

2013 marks the 10th anniversary of Campus Europae. A decade is an excellent vantage point to look back in order to trace the main axis of the CE mission and take stock of what has been achieved.

The idea of the creation of CE dates from the 1999 German Presidency of the EU, and is therefore contemporary to the Bologna Declaration. In 2001, a group of universities was invited to attend a meeting under the patronage of the Luxembourg Government to make public the will to create the European University Foundation - Campus Europae. The establishment of the foundation took the following two years, leading to the formal launch of Campus Europae in 2003, with a particularly numerous presence of universities from the newest EU countries in Central and Eastern Europe and even from European countries outside the EU.

The affinities between CE and Bologna are not just in timing but, far more important, in a shared vision of the construction of a "European Higher

Education Area". Mobility of students and scholars is crucial towards reaching that end, rightly figuring first in the stated aims of the Bologna declaration. Despite being an unqualified success, the EU Erasmus programme poses some quite severe restrictions in terms of access to and quality of the experience offered to students. Campus Europae set from the start more ambitious goals for itself, encapsulated in the designation Erasmus+, placing longer and more structured mobility and multilingualism as core rules of the project. The two are closely related, the learning of the language of the country(ies) of stay being a prerequisite for a real understanding of its culture and people. As such they should both be part of the build up of a real European citizenship.

Regarding mobility CE set the goal of offering the students the opportunity of studying two full years in two different countries other than their home country during their bachelor and master studies. In the course of their

stay they are expected to achieve the B1 level in mastering the language of the two host countries. The students who achieve that and complete successfully the curricular part of their studies are awarded the CE degree.

These are really ambitious targets. In order to reach them the programs of studies in the host countries should be carefully planned and proper support given to language learning. That is only possible by providing fora where the academics from the partner universities examine the different curricular offers available and define matrices of equivalences to serve as the basis for the definition of programs of studies of the mobile students. The subject committees on Business, Engineering, Humanities, Natural Sciences and Teacher Training, are such fora where CE invests very significant resources. On the learning of the language of the host countries a teaching and learning platform, Hook-Up, was developed. Using the model of blended learning, learning materials on the languages of all the countries of the partner universities were developed and online support to the students is provided by teachers who are native speakers. This allows the mobile students to reach level A in the mastering of the language of the host country before the mobility period starts. Knowledge and skills, be it of the subject of study of the student or of the languages and cultures of the host countries, must

however be complemented by providing students with the means and opportunities to exercise and develop their innovative spirit. Hence CE supports from the start a Student Council joining the students from all partner universities. And the Student Council is actually a key contributor in the formation of active European citizens. The Tour d'Europe and Riding for Your Rights projects, proposed and organised by students, have been very successful in fostering a spirit of initiative, collaboration and friendship among the students and in spreading the word about CE and its goals and activities. The theme of human rights is particularly dear to CE, in part due to the fact that some of its partner universities are from countries where basic civil rights have only recently been recognized, and another one, the European Humanities University, is currently in exile in Lithuania due to the human rights situation in Belarus, its country of origin. Hence, in collaboration with the University of Luxembourg, CE annually hosts the Luxembourg Forum on Human Rights.

This publication gives an overview of the history and activities of CE since its inception through the words of some of its key actors. The original concept is described by Konrad Schily, a founding father of CE, in "The great challenge: educating a new generation of Europeans". "Why Europe needs initiatives like Campus Europae", by Erna Hennicot Schoepges, who was the Minister of Cul-

ture, Research and Higher Education of the Luxembourg government when CE was created under its auspices, and thus played an important role in making it a reality, describes how the original concept came into being. Noel Whelan, CE's first president, in its text puts CE in the context of the creation of the European Higher Education Area and its contributions to it. Doris Pack, MEP and rapporteur of the European Parliament for the new generation of mobility programmes, focuses on the added value CE brings to Erasmus.

The empirical data shows that there remains a big economic barrier to mobility, with students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds being virtually unable to experience mobility during their courses of study, hence being effectively prevented access to enjoy the support of the European mobility programs. Achim Meyer auf der Heyde in "Keeping the social dimension alive" refers to that as "a neglected promise" of the Bologna process. CE believes that one of the ways to fight the access problem is to offer the mobile student the possibility of combining study with part-time paid work. This is what the CE LEP program offers. In "Bologna meets Lisbon" Birgit Brödermann, who has been actively involved in the organisation of some of these LEPs, reports on the experiences of some of the LEP students.

Estela Pereira, former President of CE and before that the first coordinator of the Nat-

ural Sciences Subject Committee, describes the history, achievements and challenges of the Subject Committees. Wilfred Hartmann, chair of the Teacher Training SC gives the rationale for the central role the knowledge of languages plays within CE, and explains how that is being put into practice

Two CE students, Katharina Miller and Julian Walkowiak, both former presidents of the Student Council, describe the projects they directed and which constitute landmark events in the history of CE. The former reports on "Tour d' Europe" and the latter on "Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life".

CE does not just deepen and enrich the students mobility experiences. It has also geographically enlarged the scope of participating countries by including in the network universities from non-EU countries. Such is the case of the University of Novi Sad, in Serbia, whose former rector, Fuada Stankovic in "Tearing Down the Borders in Higher Education" describes the new experience of being a full member of the Campus Europae network.

"Putting Human Rights and Higher Education on the Agenda" by Sjur Bergan from the Council of Europe explains the centrality of the issue of Human Rights and the important role the Luxembourg Forum on Human Rights can play in putting the issue on the agenda of the universities in Europe, where

at present it does not enjoy the attention it attracts in other regions of the world.

The existence of Campus Europae is made possible by the government of Luxembourg whose unaltering support is proof of its deep commitment to further the European Project. The text by Minister François Biltgen gives CE the assurance that it can continue to fulfil its mission and by so doing contributing to that project.

This publication concludes with the actual history of CE by Christoph Ehmann, CE's main driving force in the first decade of its existence and that will certainly continue to be so in the years to come.

Prof. Whelan

President EUF-CE
2003 - 2007

"There is no better way of engendering both such Europeanisation and a realisation of the profound European unity which transcends European diversity than by experiencing this unity for oneself"

International student programmes - the uniqueness and importance of Campus Europae

I am very pleased to have been asked to write a short contribution to this the Tenth Anniversary Pamphlet of Campus Europae. I am honoured to have been the founding President of the European University Foundation, which included Campus Europae, for its first six years. But, while I was the founding President, the real founder of Campus Europae was Dr Konrad Schily who, with some colleagues and with the help of stiftung funding from Germany (cf. details provided by Prof. Ch. Ehmann, page 63), conceived of the project and got it underway. In addition, Campus Europae was successfully developed through the continuing generosity and visionary far-sightedness of the Luxembourg Government (and its successive Ministers for Education, and its Premier Conseiller Prof. Germain Dondelinger) which funded the project each year and gave it political support. As for management: Campus Europae was very lucky to have had

the services, initially, of Mrs Uta Wolf as Secretary and, then, of Professor Dr Christoph Ehmann as its Secretary General for ten years. All these institutions and people (and their unfaltering commitment to European ideals and idealism over the years) have made Campus Europae what it is. I acknowledge the essential contribution which they have made, and I thank them for it.

So, what is the uniqueness and importance of Campus Europae ?

There are many international student exchange programmes throughout the world. Most of them have a general international focus. The uniqueness of the Campus Europae student exchange programme is that it is, at once, international in orientation and quintessentially European in focus and content. Its European focus relates to all of Europe, and not just to the European Union.

One cannot contemplate and comprehend the importance of Campus Europae without placing it in the context of the historical evolution of Europe in recent times. This evolution has many success stories to its credit, and they largely hinge around the development and expansion of the European Union and Europolitical developments of the utmost importance such as e.g. the fall of the Berlin Wall and the Unification of Germany, the Single European Market, and relative prosperity in most European states, with safety and freedom being the prevailing norm.

So, the European glass is “half full” rather than being “half empty”. But, the fact that the glass is not full gives pause for thought. For all its achievements, Europe is not doing a great job when it comes to instilling a sense of shared history and purpose (a quintessential Europeanisation) amongst post-war generations. And there is no better way of engendering both such Europeanisation and a realisation of the profound European unity which transcends European diversity than by experiencing this unity for oneself.

It is in precisely in this context that Campus Europae makes its most important strategic contribution.

Campus Europae has been specifically designed and developed to be an avenue through which young student Europeans

can connect and identify themselves, in a practical and learning way, with Europe. They do this by spending, initially, one academic year from their four year degree academic programme abroad (i.e. outside of their native country) at a Campus Europae partner university in another European country..... as part of their degree studies. During this year, they learn the language of their host country and experience, at first hand, its culture, traditions, and its people. They gradually embed themselves in a society which, up to their arrival, they may very well have thought of as alien. When this first year is satisfactorily completed, the Campus Europae students undertake a second year at another Campus Europae university in another European country. In this way, Campus Europae has been generating a stream of European-oriented citizens who have experienced at first hand, and are knowledgeable about the diversity of European cultures and, most importantly, are aware of and understand the deep and rich European unity which runs through this diversity.

In addition to this student experience, Campus Europae, through its member universities, contributes to the achievement of the aims and objectives of the Bologna process, the European credit mobility aspirations, and the Erasmus programme.

The quintessential European DNA of Cam-

pue Europae, and the dedication and commitment of its member universities to expanding the Campus Europae ethos and to involving more students in it, enhances and promulgates the European ideal and resolve. This enhancement would be enriched and deepened greatly if European policy makers were to rationalise and increase the monetary incentives for European students who are willing to embark upon the European mobility experience.

The rich, international European experience which Campus Europae offers leads to Europe reconnecting with its youth and to

generating European citizens. I look forward to the day when all European students will have the means and the opportunity to embark on the Campus Europae experience.

I am proud and honoured to have been allowed play a small part in this most import project.

Ms. Erna
Hennicot-
Schoepges

Luxembourg Minister of
Higher Education and
Research 1999 - 2004

Member of the
European Parliament
2004 - 2009

*“There was no
hesitation, a clear
answer, a strong
commitment”*

Why Europe needs Campus Europae

Involved in the history of establishing Campus Europae in Luxembourg as the minister responsible for higher education and research, I remember the first meeting with Prime Minister Juncker, Dr. Konrad Schily and Christa Thoben. There was no hesitation, a clear answer, a strong commitment by the head of government and the public announcement in the inaugural speech of the new government in May 2000. The history of Campus Europae links the initiative to the German presidency of the EU in 1999, not followed up however in Germany, but transmitted to the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg. At this moment the Grand Duchy had not yet its own University.

In spite of the clear approval of the aim of student's mobility linked to Campus Europae the way of establishing it as a foundation in Luxembourg was paved with many obstacles. These were linked to the complexity of the agenda. I learned in these days that negotiations between universities, their rec-

tors and professors were nearly as difficult as those I was used to in my political responsibilities. Establishing a foundation with all the legal background needed and sufficient financial support was neither an easy task. At this time of the beginning universities regular conferences, held in Luxembourg and hosted by my ministry, were organized with partner universities, some of which are still today members of the project.

Mobility between Universities

Since the publication of the white paper on “Teaching and Learning, towards the learning society”, edited in 1996 on the initiative of Commissioner Edith Cresson with the agreement of two other Commissioners, and the “Green paper on the obstacles to transnational mobility of students, the debate was ongoing in the European Council of Education ministers. The obstacles being various, initiatives were taken to improve language skills in national education systems, as well as improving the Erasmus

program, that had been initiated in 1987 by the European Commission. In the meantime the Bologna Declaration, signed in 1999 by Twenty-nine countries, had put the topic of inter-university mobility on the agenda of many European universities. A serious concern of ministers was the reshaping of higher education and research in the EU, linked to the Lisbon strategy, launched in 2000 by the European Council. It should have been the response to the facing challenges of globalization and therefore promoted a higher investment by all member states in research and innovation.

Considering however the independence of universities the shift of curricula to the promoted system by the Bologna Declaration of 3-5-8 had its own speed: some universities

quickly transformed their diploma in bachelors, masters and PhD, many others kept their own system. Mobility of students did not progress so much in order to make it possible for students to change within one single study course the university, without needing supplementary time to get a diploma.

Campus Europae became a very interesting alternative to create a network of universities committed to mobility. As I was from 2004-2009 a member of the European Parliament, I arranged a meeting with Commissioner Jan Figel and Campus Europae in the offices in Brussels. A very fruitful exchange finally led to an agreement with the European Commission on behalf of the Erasmus program.

No longer involved in higher education business in Luxembourg since 2004, it was my pleasure to learn from Dr. Ehmann the last news and to see how the fragile commitment of the beginning has become a reality. The location in Munsbach as well as the network of now 19 universities has brought many students to the country.

Student's mobility in Luxembourg.

In the Grand Duchy mobility had however been a very successful way to avoid creating the country's own university until the beginning of the 21st century. Luxembourg students had to quit their home country if they wanted to study at a university. This was a good system to improve the knowledge of other countries, traditions and cultures among high skilled professionals among the population. However, the low rate of university students among residents in Luxembourg and the high rate of brain drain of students staying abroad, were a solid motivation to change the system. The debate about the necessity to create its own university was ongoing since half a century, ending in 2003, the year when the University of Luxembourg was created as a research-led University with three faculties. It has been built up under the rules of compulsory mobility and multilingualism. Campus Europae and the experiences made by its initiators have for sure inspired the model.

Dr. Konrad
Schily

Initiator of Campus
Europae
President of the
University of Witten
1982 - 1999

*"Europe should
rather capitalise on
its key asset, that
is its diversity in
terms of cultures
and languages, by
providing a space for
free and unrestrained
cooperation"*

The great challenge: educating a new generation of Europeans

At the Opening Conference of Campus Europae at the 20th and 21st of June 2001 in Luxembourg Dr. Schily described the concept "Campus Europae" as followed. Text was shortened partially:

The essence of the initiative "Campus Europae" can be summarised in very simple words:

For the sake of the idea of Europe, and in order to give the young people of Europe a space to meet, let every European country donate one of its universities to Europe. Or, to put it another way, place one of its universities in a position to connect with other European universities in a free, impartial manner, so that out of this common effort, a European cultural space – a "Campus Europae" – may come into being, where at least some of the young people of Europe and of the entire world can move freely.

Because Europe has always

been culturally fruitful when its nations engaged in peaceful cultural encounters. For over nine hundred years now, Europe's universities have been a constitutive element of European culture. And the more that freedom of spoken and written expression, freedom to carry out research, to teach and to study – as well as the free movement of the people – were guaranteed, the more the universities were able to contribute to cultural development.

However, the more universities' freedom was restricted by small minded-nationalistic or even tyrannical systems, the more any progress was drained away from them. Under these circumstances, the upholders of culture and free thinking – whether they were teachers, researchers or students – were forced to be silent or had to escape from persecution, often by fleeing their own countries. The examples are countless and they reach into the most recent past of only some ten

years ago. We would like to phrase it this way: complete freedom and individual responsibility are prerequisites for cultural development in general – and for universities in particular.

The new realities – ever accelerating internationalism and globalisation – exceed the rather narrow frame conditions of nation states.

Universities should probably be the last to complain about these developments and their consequences. After all, science that originated in these very universities – particularly in the areas of natural sciences and technology – is both one fundamental cause of, as well as an ongoing impetus for this development.

Nevertheless, universities cannot simply be reduced to establishments for research, teaching and services: They are arenas for discourse and for encounters between and within generations. At their best, they are venues for transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary dialogue, and – let me emphasize this – if they are to keep up with the present times, universities must be settings of international and cultural importance.

Without a very practical and tangible experience of the respective “others”, the young people of Europe cannot develop the skills required for their present and future professional lives. This in itself is no news. Therefore, nearly every European university has a number of international co-operation

agreements nowadays. Moreover, there are many programmes for international student mobility, for the exchange of scientists, and so on. However, we also know that all these programmes often do not carry through. We know that – with the exception of the UK – the international stream of students bypasses Europe to a large extent, and the processes of mutual acknowledgement (for example performance records) are rather cumbersome.

This sounds all too familiar when we think about other areas of European politics – and I have to agree with those commentators who interpret the results of the recent Irish referendum on Europe as a signal by citizens that Europe has become very intransparent and remote to them.

Given the existing global higher education industry, we believe that the most promising way in which Europe can respond to this challenge, is not through standardisation and uniformity. Europe should rather capitalise on its key asset, that is its diversity in terms of cultures and languages, by providing a space for free and unrestrained cooperation.

Hence, we propose that several universities from Eastern, Central and Western Europe join together and form an alliance. As in each good alliance, the different members should maintain their individuality. Identities should not be given up, as it is the diversity

that makes each of them a valuable member of the alliance. The individual members of the alliance should be prepared to appreciate and adjust to these differences. The more independent members are, the more likely they will be able to bring this about. Paraphrasing Wilhelm von Humboldt, one could conclude: The more a society focusses on strengthening the individual, and the more the individual is prepared to contribute to society, the more free and peaceful a society can be.

In our case this means, that in order for each individual university to adapt to an alliance, it must be able to operate fully responsibly. In other words, the individual members of the alliance must be able to act independently and responsibly. It is for this reason, that the working group that I represent today, has suggested to establish a European University Foundation as an organisational platform and coordinating body in that regard. Its constitution has been designed to enable members to directly discuss, negotiate and reach agreements with other members.

The foundation's main purpose consists in encouraging and facilitating students to conduct their studies in at least two – or even three countries – whereby the foundation would ensure that the transfer between universities of a “Campus Europe” would take place smoothly and efficiently.

Once this goal has been reached, we expect that participating universities soon should have 30% or more foreign students

enrolled. This will immediately and fundamentally affect university culture. The result will be – I am sure! – a more open, freer and livelier university, which hopefully would also be more creative and innovative. All of this will in turn positively and equally affect teaching – and research. Each member university would then host a Europe “en miniature”.

The goal is by no means a standardised European curriculum, rather an efficiently and effectively agreed and coordinated set of courses of study. Agreements among member universities and corresponding contracts should only be signed, if considered to be consistent with the individual university's ideas as well as its conception of itself. The issue is not uniformity, the issue is equal partnership between and among the members of the alliance.

“Campus Europae” stands for both unity and diversity. Just as the different airline carriers face the challenge to either fail as an individual company or to cooperate with other carriers and prosper – see for example the Star Alliance –, many European universities are facing the question of how to remain competitive in a global higher education market.

Which overall strategic choices the alliance will make, will be left up to its future members.

It is well possible that other university alliances will be set up in the future – and they might even become competitors to the “Campus Europe” alliance. But they will have to catch up, as it is he who moves first who has the significant competitive edge.

Let me conclude by summarising the five main advantages:

- The European states have created a strong union, which more countries are urgently hoping to join. It is now crucial to systematically arrange encounters for future leaders and executives – and to do so by allowing for a high degree of freedom, trusting their will and potential.
- In an ever intensifying global competition for the brightest minds, universities would be in a far better position to master this challenge as partners within an alliance for a very simple reason: Their future will be international or – it will not be at all. Transcontinental partnerships should not be ruled out; the alliance might even be a precondition for such partnerships in the future.
- With the “Campus Europe” initiative, an institution would be established that considers Europe’s diversity not as a weakness but as a strength; an asset rather, that can be put to use as such.
- Our suggestions do not contradict the Bologna-, Salamanca- and Prague declarations. In our view, they complement each other. We consider our suggestion a

faster and more independent approach to achieving the goals put forward in these declarations.

- I believe it to be impossible to fully fathom today how positive the effects of such an opening to the world would be for each participating university and each participating country – and thus for all of Europe.

This opening conference became possible thanks to the strong support by Minister Hennicot-Schoepges and Prime Minister Juncker. In Europe, their commitment and contribution to European unification is highly appreciated, as is their great experience, their pragmatism to include visions and concerns of smaller countries.

We appreciate their endeavours to uphold economic and social solidarity, especially towards less powerful individuals. Let me thank both once again for making possible this conference! Their support today shows their strong commitment to intellectual freedom as one of the important prerequisites for economic and cultural prosperity.

Achim Meyer auf
der Heyde

Secretary-General
Deutsches
Studentenwerk

Vice-President of the
European Council for
Student Affairs

*“Extended and
deepened cooperation
between student
services and other
networks will be
needed, to realize the
ambitious goals of
social dimension”*

Keeping the social dimension alive

Social dimension and the Bologna Process – a neglected promise

One of the ambitious goals of the Bologna process has been formulated by ‘realizing the social dimension’, next to comparable degree structures, the mutual recognition of degrees and credits points, the focus on learning outcomes, introducing quality standards and the aim to increase mobility of students and staff: In 2001, the European ministers for Higher Education met in Prague and “emphasized the social dimension of mobility”. In 2003, at the meeting in Berlin they “reaffirm(ed) the importance of the social dimension of the Bologna Process”. In 2005, at the Bergen meeting, the ministers recognized the social dimension as “a constituent part of the EHEA and a necessary condition for the attractiveness and competitiveness of the EHEA” while “quality Higher Education should be equally accessible to all,” and students should be enabled to “complete their studies without obstacles relat-

ed to their social and economic background”. This “includes measures taken by governments to help students, especially from socially disadvantaged groups, in financial and economic aspects and to provide them with guidance and counseling services”. In 2007 at the London meeting, the ministers reaffirmed “to continue (their) efforts to provide adequate student services (...) to widen participation at all levels on the basis of equal opportunity.” In 2009, at the meeting in Leuven they declared that “access to Higher Education should be widened by fostering the potential of students from underrepresented groups and by providing adequate conditions for the completion of their studies”. This involves improvements in the learning environment, removing barriers to study, and creating the appropriate economic conditions for students to be able to benefit from the study opportunities at all levels”. Eventually, in 2012 at the meeting Bucharest they wanted “step up our efforts to-

wards underrepresented groups to develop the social dimension of Higher Education, reduce inequalities and provide adequate student support services, counseling and guidance, flexible learning paths and alternative access routes, including recognition of prior learning“.

Social Dimension – the reality

In this context Social Dimension is characterized by many facets: financial support, participation of students in decision-making processes, data collection, student services, participation of underrepresented groups, diversity etc. Following those goals, exempt from the participation in decision-making processes and the collection of data too little happened in realizing the social Dimension since 1999. There were no concrete measures taken by the national authorities to increase student support and mobility. Apart from a handful of financial fostering programs on the national and European level, such as the Erasmus program, until today no systematic support to increase study access, retention and study success or international mobility has been put in place. As the Eurostudent report shows, the access to Higher Education still depends on higher familiar origin among a major part of the Bologna Member States, and this result is as well transferable to the access to student mobility. And on the other hand remarkable measures to provide adequate student services have been neglected by the minis-

ters for Education and this in opposition with their statements in the different Bologna Communiqués. In addition, the stakeholders of student services were in the majority of countries not involved the Bologna Ministers' decisions. In order to challenge this absence of involvement, a fruitful cooperation between Campus Europae and the student services umbrella organization, the European Council for Student Affairs (ECStA) took place by organising common conferences, workshops and meetings with committees of the European Parliament to promote students mobility and sufficient student services.

Social dimension – the challenges

UNESCO emphasized “the importance of student support services and the key role of its professionals” for access and study success. In addition, the Berlin International Bologna Conference 2011 has shown that the demand on Student Affairs and Services grows on a worldwide level and the in-depth survey, presented by the European University Association (EUA) underlines the need for student support systems in a globalized system of Higher Education Institutions. The attractiveness of a Higher Education regions – in our case the EHEA - will depend on the student services as a key factor and inalienable precondition to promote international mobility, which may be translated in the Bologna process as the social dimension. Therefore an extended and

deepened cooperation between student services and other networks will be needed, to realize the ambitious goals of social dimension. This kind of cooperation doesn't aim at harmonizing the structures of student services in the Bologna Area, but promoting cohesion between the participating countries. For student mobility one necessary precondition is cohesion, which at the same time for its realization requires networks like Campus Europae.

Doris Pack

MEP

Chair of the Education
and Culture Committee

*“Young people
studying and living
in several European
countries, knowing
different cultures,
speaking several
languages are living
the European idea
and develop to be
responsible citizens of
the EU”*

Campus Europae, a source of new ideas

26 years ago, in 1987, the Erasmus programme started. The idea of Erasmus was to give young Europeans the opportunity to spend some time at a university abroad. Who did predict back then that Erasmus would become such a success story?

When Erasmus has been launched, there was no European Education Policy laid down in the Treaties. Hence, it marks kind of a starting point of our common engagement in the field of Education. Erasmus soon became the driving force of student's mobility. The fact that more integration in the field of European Higher Education was needed led to the Bologna Process which was launched in 1999. The Bologna process has aimed since then at creating a Common European Higher Education Area. Through the harmonisation of standards, mobility and exchange should be facilitated. Shortly after that, in 2003, Campus Europae (CE) was founded; among the initiators were such

great Europeans as Helmut Kohl and Jean-Claude Juncker. For 10 years now, Campus Europae has contributed to mobility of students and high quality of Education.

Today we can say that the Erasmus programme is a success. It has enabled and enables many students from all over Europe to study abroad. Students do not only get competent knowledge at the host university; they get to know another country, the people, the culture, the language. Young people participating in Erasmus are living what being European actually means.

Currently, we are working on the new EU programme for Education and Training, Youth and Sport 2014 - 20. Less bureaucracy, more efficiency and simplification are the main focus in this future programme to overcome remaining obstacles and to improve Higher Education in Europe further. More flexibility is needed in order to adapt the mobility ac-

tivities to the Bologna reforms and the new degree structures that have been established throughout Europe - namely Bachelor, Master and PhD degrees. The programme will also have to boost the mobility of academics and teachers. Not only pupils and students, but also lecturers have to experience the unique value of a temporary stay abroad.

Furthermore, unfortunately, problems still exist in terms of recognition of courses and qualifications gained abroad. It is necessary to improve recognition and credit transfer by implementing for instance ECTS correctly in a comparable way across Europe. More than so far, an unbureaucratic and student-friendly way of handling recognition should be a precondition to take part in the Erasmus programme.

Another important aspect is the free access for all students to the programme, regardless of their educational, social and cultural background. Students not having enough money must also get the chance to study abroad. Social exclusion is an important problem which we have to tackle. Thus, the Commission's proposal to create a financial instrument to help students secure funding for a Masters degree outside their home Member State is an important step in the right direction. This European-level student loan guarantee facility should enable thousands of students to complete a Masters De-

gree abroad.

I very much welcome the attention Campus Europae pays to the educational programme and the suggestions it makes to better implement it. The CE's request to create opportunities to combine part-time studies with part-time internships during an Erasmus stay also is a means to help students financing their stay abroad which I consider very important. Likewise appears their criticism on the fact that Erasmus students can only spend one semester or academic year at one university. It would be an important step if we could achieve that students can participate in Erasmus more than one time. Young people studying and living in several European countries, knowing different cultures, speaking several languages are living the European idea and develop to be responsible citizens of the EU.

In the 10 years that it exists, Campus Europea has been doing a lot to support the process of striving for improvement, the constant search for inspirations. Building up on the infrastructure of the Erasmus programme, CE has always aimed at providing more quality, boosting mobility and overcoming obstacles. Its achievements provide us with examples of good practice and are an inspiration to the EU education policy. The CE calls itself rightly "laboratory of mobility". It is a source of new ideas always trying to find the best solution, to create the best possible

opportunity for the students and support them in the preparation of and during their stay abroad. And moreover, it shares its new findings with the public and EU policy makers in order to really cause change.

I am convinced that also in the future, we will be partners in our common engagement in mobility and education. I congratulate Campus Europae's' for its 10th anniversary and wish all the best for the continuation of the project!

Prof. Estela
Pereira

EUF-CE Ombudsperson

EUF-CE President
2007 - 2009

Chair of the
Natural Science
Subject Committee

"The Bologna Process is now formally implemented, but in practice there are still many outstanding problems, such as the definition of learning outcomes, the evaluation of student workload, the 1st cycle employability, the introduction of research in the degree programs (...)"

Towards 99% of Academic recognition Subject Committees

The Subject Committees were introduced since the very beginning of Campus Europae. It was clearly assumed that a high quality mobility, with full recognition of the studies abroad, could only be achieved if academic staff had the opportunity of comparing the degree programs in their own field.

Seven Subject Committees were established: Business, Engineering, Humanities and Social Sciences, Law, Medicine, Natural Sciences and Teacher Training. One first step was the feasibility studies. It became obvious a distinction between the essentially mono disciplinary subjects: Business, Law and Medicine and the others that involve a wide list of programs. Therefore the approach for the multidisciplinary subjects was dictated by practical reasons. For instance, most of the participants in Natural Sciences were Physicists, while most of the participants in engineering were Electric/Electronic engi-

neers. Thus in the first phase the feasibility studies were directed to the areas that had most representatives in the committee. Teacher Training concentrated only in the didactics component, without discussion of the subject related components.

Most of the participating Institutions had no previous contacts with each other and the degree of previous participation in mobility programs, like ERASMUS, was very different. However, after a few meetings that were mainly devoted to trust building and sharing of details about degree programs practical aspects of finding correspondences between courses could be achieved. These feasibility studies were presented in the form of matrices. Each University selected a number of courses of the different host Universities totaling 60 credits for a full year. These matrices had implicit ex ante recognition, by replacement of an equivalent number of courses at the home University.

It is to be stressed that this is a unique opportunity Campus Europae offers to its members. As a matter of fact this type of meetings foreseen in the first phase of ERASMUS, (ICP's) was discontinued. The idea was that the development of standardized information about the degree programs at each University will render the meetings between academic staff unnecessary. However this is not the day to day situation and nothing can replace the face to face meetings where all problems concerning mobility can be discussed. This pioneering work made possible to launch a pilot phase limited to the areas that have been worked out in more detail.

Pilot Phase of the Subject Committees

This was the opportunity of putting to test the models developed by the subject committees with actual movers. It was clear that although the experience was shown to be in general very positive, some aspects have been overlooked. One first issue came with the thesis work. Some students did the work at the host institution but with the distant supervision of a home professor, the exam being carried out on their return. Obviously the number of credits awarded at the host institution fell short of the expected 60 ECTS. Also it came out that some Institutions adopted the term recognition not in the sense of replacement of courses, but of acknowledgement of extra work, indicated in the additional information in the Diploma

Supplement. Also the fact that the implementation of ECTS was at different stages in the different Universities have shown that there was not a common idea about their role. These findings prompted further activities for the Subject Committees to define ways of deepening the mobility procedures and solving the problems found.

The impact of the Bologna Process

All the work done so far by the Subject Committees were done on the basis of the traditional pre Bologna "long" cycles. In a way these long cycles allowed for more flexibility in the mobility, as usually the student could take, at the host University, course units of different years in the degree program. At the time only Italy had adopted the 3+2 Bologna model and France had a nearly Bologna compatible model.

There were two key issues with the introduction of the Bologna process: the different timetable for the implementation in the different Universities and the different duration of the cycles. Thus we have Universities with a 3+2, a 4+1 and a 4+2 model for the first two cycles. Therefore the Subject Committees were faced during the consolidation of the Bologna Process with the task of updating the recognition matrices and defining mobility windows. In practice the Bologna process facilitates vertical mobility between cycles, but limits somehow horizontal mobility. Furthermore in many Universities the introduction of a 1st cycle made the curricula

less flexible than before. Also the 2nd cycle became more diversified, making more difficult recognition paths.

An extra problem is the administrative question of allowing a student of a given cycle to take courses of a different one while being in the host University. These considerations illustrate how demanding was the challenge put on the Subject Committees to find solutions for these problems.

The consolidation phase

It can be considered that nowadays the Subject Committees reached a maturity phase. They are called to play an increasing role in defining good mobility practices. Therefore we can consider two different aspects:

- The definition of recognition matrices for an increasing number of degrees
- The deepening of the cooperation between the Universities.

It is obvious that recognition matrices can only be worked out by the professors in the corresponding subject area. This became a challenge for the interdisciplinary subject committees. Some subject committees started by allowing representatives of different areas to participate in the meetings. This was clearly feasible when there were only a few Universities represented in that area and the total number of areas was small: for instance Natural Sciences worked in Physics

and Biochemistry. To enlarge the number of areas covered by the subject committees it was necessary to take a new, more flexible approach. The idea was to create subgroups in those areas where there was a cooperation interest from 3 or more Universities. They will have the clearly defined task of building recognition matrices. These subgroups activities are part of the activities of the Subject Committee and must report to the chair of the Subject Committee. A coordinator for the group must be appointed by the Subject Committee. This strategy has been progressively adopted by the multidisciplinary committees.

The Bologna Process is now formally implemented, but in practice there are still many outstanding problems, such as the definition of learning outcomes, the evaluation of student workload, the 1st cycle employability, the introduction of research in the degree programs, the introduction of common degrees (joint, double...), the acceptance of credits in the learning of a foreign language as part of the degree. The subject committees may play an important role to contribute to the deepening of the understanding of the Bologna Process and to the internationalization of the Universities. These are fundamental aspects that guaranty high quality mobility. The Subject Committees are an ideal Forum of discussion of these problems.

The Subject Committees in the future

As in all organizations there is always the need of improvement in procedures and diversification of tasks. This is clearly a time of change for the Subject Committees. Now that the curricula have to a high extent being settled, the update. But they have an important role in deepening all aspects related to mobility task of building matrices does no longer require a detailed and time consuming, that will bring added value to the Institutions for their participation in Campus Europae. Some aspects have not yet been developed, like joint research projects that could facilitate thesis work, both at Master and PHD level. The diversity of 2nd cycle programs could be dealt with by the implementation of degrees with a strong common approach. There is some experience of joint and double degrees. All have in common a lot of complicated and time consuming preparation. Why not could Campus Europae contribute with a more flexible way of establishing common acceptable degrees? Clearly it is a matter for each subject committee to define its own priorities.

From this over view of the activities of the Subject Committees two key aspects emerge. So far they played an essential role in the task of defining mobility pathways, thus fulfilling one key aspect of Campus Europae: ex ante guaranteed recognition of the studies abroad. New activities require

the continuing existence of the subject committees in order to keep on the improvement of the quality of the cooperation between Universities. Subject Committees are and will continue to be an essential part of Campus Europae.

Katharina
Miller

EUF-CE Student Council
President 2003 - 2005

*"CE encourages
students to be active
citizens both at
university and
beyond"*

A student centered network

Currently, the news about the EU is dominated by the Euro and worst-case scenarios. While the British feel themselves in the need of a different approach to Europe (a very euphemistical expression for the announced in-out referendum on Britain's membership of the EU before the end of 2017), there are also shouts for even more Europe.

I think many of us totally disagree with this negative and solely currency-orientated image of the EU. I had one of my personal experiences with an open-minded, positive thinking, democratic and value-orientated European network ten years ago when I was getting engaged with Campus Europae (CE), which has been focusing on "education, youth and the promotion of human contacts."

Within CE, the students' voice has mattered from the start. It was the students who planned and organized the so-called "Tour d'Europe", which start-

ed in September 2003. This CE project was meant to be an evaluation and promotion tour throughout Europe (European Union and Eastern Europe). On the one hand, twenty-four students of the - at that time - eleven CE member universities evaluated the faculties (like the quality of the food in the cafeterias and the subjects taught at the faculties) as well as certain special aspects of each university and its city like accommodation, mobility and costs, costs of living, tuition fees, if there were contact persons, etc.

On the other hand, these students saw themselves as ambassadors of CE. They wanted to express their identification with CE goals and therefore wanted to promote the network. Hence, they created the Tour d'Europe logo as well as its homepage, they wrote newspaper articles, gave radio and newspaper interviews, they organised the tour themselves and prepared the universities' presentations.

From the very beginning, the students' self image within CE was that they are essential and indispensable, and that they could wholly identify with this network. They were aware of the importance of the students' participation within CE to generate publicity, to live the aims of CE, to highlight feasibility and to evaluate the network and the universities. Moreover, they realised that through CE they could gain greater recognition and appreciation of what it means to be European.

facilitated the founding of the CE Student Council, which was created in November 2003. The students elaborated their own statutes, and have been organizing their own meetings and preparing the topics of the meetings up until today. Apart from organizing a second Tour d'Europe in 2005 as well as a "Right for your rights" project, which started in 2010, the Student Council created a buddy-network and pocket guides to support and to ease the adaption of CE students to their host university and its city.

The very crucial and important task of the Student Council has been and still is the approach to the so-called social dimension. Something that is focussed on in literature about European academia is free movement of students, but still the social dimension of the student mobility remains a challenging issue.

How can students who are also parents themselves afford a student exchange, what happens if the studies depend on a student job and how can handicapped students actually organise their exchange. Already in 2005 and on this matter, the Student Council elaborated a policy paper "Attaining social fairness in student mobility," requesting the development of "a second grant system generation capable of providing more competent help to the students who cannot afford to engage in mobility programs by themselves." One of the network's clear strategies and outcome of this students' policy paper has been the "Learning Employability Places (LEP)," where CE offers study-related working places in companies, administrations, hospitals, teaching institutions and NGOs while the students get prepared by the language learning module "Hook up!" and benefit from a monthly grant provided by CE.

Last but not least, another issue which the Student Council and all (CE) students deal with is the challenge of ensuring full recognition of the foreign learning experience. One gets the impression that there is nothing worse in this fast and quickly moving world than losing time during your studies. CE has been offering solutions to this problem, which in my opinion is ironically and primarily imposed by people who had the possibility to study without any time limits. The CE subject committees guarantee the full

recognition of courses attended at the host university through their elaborate matrices. The positive outcome is that a CE student never loses time and always gains a lot of experience in all aspects.

In sum, one can say that CE provides the most important lesson that a European student could possibly learn, a lesson called "democracy." CE encourages students to be active citizens both at university and beyond and to be part of the "Club d'Europe." Then again, CE is aware of the problems which mobile students experience (and tries to solve them), as well as profiting from students' solution-oriented ideas. Finally, CE is what Europe is all about. And CE students have the best approach to it.

Julian
Walkowiak

EUF-CE Student Council
President 2010 - 2012

*"Ride For Your Rights!
movement is striving
for: Education as a
basis for Europe's
future and student
mobility as a main
driver for mutual
understanding and
self-development"*

Ride for Your Rights!

The Student Council – the observing eye, the protectionist and advocate of student rights, a mobile co-working space, a greenhouse for motivated and aspiring persons, a fountain of ideas and the gearwheel of student projects. Any of the mentioned descriptions characterises the specific group of students who have made it their goal to contribute to the success of Campus Europae year in and year out. As chance would have it, in 2011 the Student Council consisted of a generation who decided to promote programme in a somewhat unconventional fashion. One idea, arisen from own experiences in student exchange, was proposed to the EUF-CE Board of Directors in the form of a seemingly impossible and lunatic project and was carried unanimously, much to the surprise of the students themselves. This day marked the beginning of a campaign that pedalled Campus Europae half way to the moon by now, while grabbing the attention of Olympic gold medallists,

Human Rights advocates and authorities in European and national politics.

The project *Ride for your Rights! It's time to (ex)change your life* was started by the Student Council with the primary goal to raise awareness of all existing obstacles to student mobility in Europe. To meet this goal, an effective tool was needed to attract a maximum of attention from the media and stakeholders of student mobility. As a first step, a Manifesto was composed which should serve as the backbone of the project and be presented in front of students and decision making bodies across Europe. The Manifesto should express what the Ride For Your Rights! movement is striving for: Education as a basis for Europe's future and student mobility as a main driver for mutual understanding and self-development. As a next step, an organising committee was called together which should carefully look into all necessary logistical preparations for the endeavour. In a

final step, the executive team was formed and the mission was made public: an international crowd of students should ride their bicycles from Novi Sad to St. Petersburg to present the Manifesto and gather as much support as possible from representatives of European stakeholders and institutions, from representatives of universities and the civil society at large. Everything that happened ever since the first day of cycling for student mobility in July 2011, is a small story of success in the eyes of the Student Council.

In brief, in summer 2011 over a hundred people from 18 different nations climbed on their bicycles and took part in the 5000 km journey from the Balkans to Russia. Day after day, they cycled across the continent to deliver the message of the Manifesto in 12 different countries. They met with students, rectors and Education experts, politicians and outstanding citizens and discussed all the obstacles to student mobility. The meetings with authorities ranged from being received by representatives of the European Commission, to Ministers of Education and Science, to meetings with numerous mayors, university rectors and agencies specialising in education development. The meetings catered for two important actions. Firstly, they presented the content of the Manifesto and urged interlocutors to implement necessary measures for improving and enhancing student mobility. Secondly, supporters were asked to support the project publicly

by either signing the Bike of Honour, the Manifesto, sending an endorsement letter or recording a video message for all viewers and followers of the tour. Educational workshops played a pivotal role during the 2011 edition as well. All workshops were realised in co-operation with local organisations and institutions of the visited countries. The workshops focused on topics that the Student Council considered relevant for fostering an attitude and mind-set among all participants that would stimulate each individual to live as an active citizen in society. Topics such as Human Rights, Non-violent Action, European Citizenship and Cross-border relations were covered during the tour. In addition to the workshops, Europe's history was highlighted by various study visits. Visits to e.g. Auschwitz, the Łódź Ghetto in Poland or the 9th Fort in Kaunas, Lithuania were made to motivate participants to reflect upon the atrocities of Europe's shared recent history. After a total of 73 days of cycling and an extensive programme, the mission was completed at last. The project had received media coverage in nearly all visited countries and attracted a considerable amount of noteworthy supporters from all walks of life. The successful completion of the tour itself, with all the attention it had gained along the way, was a remarkable achievement on its own. In hindsight however, the scope of the project was much larger and more rewarding as originally envisaged. The community which the project had created involved

nearly 200 young people from over 100 different clubs and organisations, all of which shared the same ideals and remained passionate about the project. This phenomenon led the Student Council and their main partner, the Erasmus Student Network, to the decision of organising a second edition of Ride for your Rights!. This time however, all efforts should be made to make the leading authorities of the European Institutions aware of the students' concerns by carrying the message directly to them.

Thus, 2012 saw a sequel of the project in a slightly adapted fashion. The year marked the 25th anniversary of the well-known ERASMUS programme on the one side and on the other side, it was the year of debating the 2014 – 2020 Multiannual Financial Framework of the EU and the upcoming generation of EU programmes. This was just the right moment to send a group of cyclists from Luxembourg directly to Strasbourg and Brussels to demand an inclusion of the stated proposals of the Ride for your Rights! Manifesto into the next generation of the Lifelong Learning Programme. With joint efforts and thorough preparations a total of five Ride for your Rights! tours were organised in different countries that year, underlying the projects acceptance beyond Campus Europae associates. The highlight remaining the Luxembourg-Brussels tour due to its exceptional and political vigour. With the support of the EUF-CE Secretariat, Ride for your

Rights! entered the hallways of the Council of Europe, the European Parliament and the European Commission at once. A Student Council delegation and participants of the tour presented the project at all three institutions within two weeks time while still insisting on better conditions for student mobility. With an ever growing community of Ride for your Rights! activists and followers, the Student Council can be proud of having created a movement that contributes to the promotion of Campus Europae in the Higher European Education Area. Within the project's two years of existence, an extensive list of education experts, European Parliamentarians, University Rectors and outstanding citizens have expressed their support to the project. Among the most renowned supporters one can find leaders such as the Secretary General of the Council of Europe, the former President of the European Parliament, the Chair of the Committee on Culture and Education of the European Parliament, the former Commissioner for Education, Culture, Multilingualism and Youth, Nobel Peace Prize nominees, Olympic gold athletes, and Guinness World Book of Record holders. The project has further been nominated for the European Charlemagne Youth Prize in 2011. The fast and positive development of the project was certainly due to the determined and diligent contribution of all students involved. However, the institutional support provided by the Secretary General of the EUF-CE has always been out-

standing and played an essential role in the forming of the project.

Preparations for a third campaign in 2013 have commenced a while ago, new partnerships are in discussion and Ride for your Rights! is looking into improving its work by becoming a legally registered organisation this year. While Campus Europae will celebrate its 10-year anniversary, Ride for your Rights! will have spread the underlying values of the institutions in over 22 countries in Europe and a very unorthodox example of active Citizenship will have travelled half way to the moon in distance, all powered by conviction and leg power of young Europeans.

Prof. Wilfried
Hartmann

Chair of the
Teacher Training
Subject Committee

*"How can we
understand varieties
of cultural concepts of
a nation pictured in its
language, if we don't
know this language?"*

Language Learning to understand the Cultural Unity in Diversity

As early as in 1958, Walter Hallstein, at that time President of the Commission of the European Economic Community, talking about the unity of European culture and the policy of uniting Europe stated: "... existing European unity is an internal unity: it is the unity of European culture, the unity of its moral foundations; it is the shared conviction of the inviolable dignity and liberty of human beings, especially freedom of opinion and of belief...."¹.

Whereas Article 22 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights, reads, "The Union respects cultural, religious and linguistic diversity" - and until today in publications, addresses and statements throughout Europe, on the level of the EU and in its member states, the

rhetoric of European cultural identity and its 'unity in diversity' is prevalent. The rhetoric sounds like a convincing programme, but when it comes to prove practically the feasibility of this approach, the truth of this assumption the attempt is coming to an early end due to the limited language proficiency of those daring to undertake this task. How can we make sure that this postulated unity really exists, how can we understand varieties of cultural concepts of a nation pictured in its language, if we don't know this language? Nobody can expect that an individual has the total active and passive command of all the languages endemic in Europe (approximately 120), nor even the 23 official languages of the EU². But the present situation can-

¹ Address delivered by Walter Hallstein, President of the Commission of the European Economic Community (EEC), at the first meeting of the Councils of the EEC and the EAEC held in Brussels on 25 January 1958. Source: Protokoll über die erste Tagung der Räte der Europäischen Wirtschaftsgemeinschaft und der Europäischen Atomgemeinschaft am 25. Januar 1958 in Brüssel, CEE EUR/CM/20f/58 mts. Brüssel: Räte der Europäischen Wirtschaftsgemeinschaft und der Europäischen Atomgemeinschaft, 25.01.1958. (c) Translation Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe (CVCE).

² Bulgarian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Irish, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovene, Spanish and Swedish.

not be tolerated, where most of our students settle for being able to communicate rough and ready in English only in addition to their home and/or national official language. This could lead very soon to a renouncement of the concept of diversity for the sake of unity.

Europe has to change its attitude towards the linguistic plurality. Instead of looking at it as a burden, it has to turn the multitude of its languages into an asset, making it necessary for professionals in all fields to be able to communicate in at least three to four languages. Therefore in 1993 I suggested a system aiming at individual language competence and performance on three different levels combined with a system of language appreciation for up to five languages.³

But today the importance of language as a gateway to the culture and society of a foreign country is still inversely proportional to the resources which are effectively being made available to impart mobile students with adequate skills in the language of their host countries. This is a central tenet of Campus Europae, as evidenced by the development of tools such as Hook-up! and the investment in other means to develop language proficiency.

In spite of the fact that most European countries are to some extent multilingual, most institutions of higher education are monolingual, with a limited use of English as additional lingua franca and a general absence of any particular policy towards the growing call for multilingual education for Europe's citizens⁴. With few exceptions, like the network of the Université Franco-Allemande/ Deutsch-französische Hochschule, the German-Polish University Viadrina in Frankfurt/Oder, or the University of Luxembourg⁵, attempts to turn universities into bi- or multi-lingual institutions or even to implement an inclusive language policy are met with some incomprehension, not being perceived as particularly relevant in the struggle for high international rankings, and may be seen as a risk to the maintenance of academic quality and a leveller of the scientific and scholarly approaches which characterise higher education across European countries. Campus Europae turns this situation to its advantage by exploring the potential of a multilingual, European campus based on the academic, cultural and linguistic diversities of its members and offering students access to the realities of up to three different academic, cultural and linguistic settings.

³ cf. Hartmann ,1993. Vom isolierten Muttersprachunterricht zum Muttersprachunterricht in mehrsprachigen Gesellschaften. Erläuterungen zu sechs Thesen. In: Pädagogik und Schule in Ost und West. 41. 1993. Heft 1. p. 12 - 20

⁴ cf. Chambers, 2003; Coleman, 2004; Phillipson, 2010

⁵ Cf. Objectifs et missions de l'UFA (<http://www.dfh-ufa.org/fr/decouvrir-lufa/objectifs-et-missions/>);

Grundordnung der Europa-Universität Viadrina, Frankfurt (Oder) vom 23.01.1995 in the version of 01.10.1999 § 1; Mission statement of the University of Luxembourg: "The mobility of students, teachers and researchers which promotes cultural openness is encouraged and constitutes an integral component of the University's strategy just like multilingualism . In these two fields, the UL intends to become a laboratory for the European university of the future."

Campus Europae – a multilingual campus

Campus Europae is “actively using Europe’s cultural diversity as a way to prepare students to develop an identity as Europeans, work in a global market and within multicultural teams”⁶. Currently the network is comprising 19 European Universities, spread across 15 European countries, but particularly notable is the range of languages it includes: 10 of the official languages of the EU are languages of instruction at its member universities, two more languages (Serbian and Turkish) of countries with a special relation to the EU, Russian (spoken widely in the three Baltic states and being the mother tongue of more than 3 million inhabitants of Germany⁷) and another one, English, serving as a lingua franca for administrative purposes and as lingua franca for students. This is giving students taking part in the programme, the chance to acquire skills in languages which are not regularly taught and learnt in our schools but which are nevertheless essential components of Europe’s linguistic and cultural diversity.

The “Concept Campus Europae” aims thus at fostering the notion of “unity in diversity” by empowering Higher Education students with multilingual skills and a sense of European identity.

Campus Europae advocates that students study abroad at least once (but preferably twice) during their studies. This means that they should spend one or two full years in two European countries where different languages are spoken and used as medium of instruction. In short, Campus Europae has set itself to promote deeper and more sustainable student mobility in the interest of achieving the wider educational goal of European citizenship. Committed to the education of multilingual and intercultural professionals for a multilingual Europe, Campus Europae aims to construct compatible academic pathways for students to enable them to follow their chosen studies in 3 different institutions / countries / languages.⁸

The Campus Europae Language Policy emerged from the recognition of the importance of language skills to support mobility and of the impact of student mobility to the development of languages, for citizens and for societies, both requiring multilingual competences, and indeed for the wider European community, desiring to protect the wealth of its linguistic and cultural diversity. It was also designed to take into account policy and economic factors which impact on the provision of foreign languages in many European universities which often hinders

⁶ cf. Campus Europae, 2003

⁷ <http://www.ifa.uni-erlangen.de/ausbildung-studium/sprachen/russisch.shtml>

⁸ To support this approach, it depends in addition to its language policy on a number of structures, namely: Subject Committees (where experts from different subject areas decide on curricular compatibility and articulation), Student Council, the Learning Employability Programme (supporting the combination of study and work abroad), a network of university Coordinators (responsible for the administrative aspects of student exchange), the Campus Europae Degree

their widespread use and learning.

Preparing for total immersion: Language Policy in Practice

To educate multilingual professionals, the knowledge of foreign languages must become a reality. However, rarely do students arrive at university being fluent in more than 1-2 foreign languages, one of which will probably be English, and once in Higher Education, they find few opportunities and even lesser motivation to acquire an additional language as they concentrate on mastering a curricular programme more often than not taught unilingually with reference to a national or linguistic context. Yet universities believe and sell the idea that their education will guarantee employment in today's European job market. But how can a student in this setting still meet the goal of acquiring the basic skill⁹ of foreign language competence? One of the solutions which externalises the provision of this skill within universities is to promote mobility amongst its students. Yet we are in a Catch22 situation, as often students who are not linguistically prepared will not jeopardise their academic results by following courses in a foreign language they do not already know. So while mobility is a plus, it is only a plus if it also offers the opportunity to maintain students' academic achieve-

ments and knowledge of the language of the host university is a pre-requisite for this, unless a shared "lingua franca" is used. But if this is the case, the exercise defeats the purpose of developing linguistic skills. One solution could be to study the host university's language prior to leaving the home university. But even at institutions, where the language departments are well developed by far not all of the European languages are offered.¹⁰ Although English, or other bridge language, often acquired in secondary education plays a key role in making study abroad a possibility, the Campus Europae approach demands the knowledge of other languages than English, frequently "less widely taught" languages. Consequently, the Campus Europae Language Policy and the adherence of European University Foundation's member universities to it is central to enabling academic study in a multilingual and multicultural context.

Under this policy, universities are called upon to create the conditions for the attainment of at least a B1 level, according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFLR), in the language of the host university and to provide accreditation of the language level reached. There are three reasons for Campus Europae to require its students to reach at least this level of competence and performance in each

⁹ The Lisbon Strategy (2000) identified IT skills, foreign languages, technological culture, entrepreneurship and social skills as the new basic skills.

¹⁰ E.g. at the university of Hamburg in its programme for students of all faculties only nine living European languages are offered, and five more in the faculty of languages

of the languages of the countries in which they study:

- Firstly, a philosophical one: the aim to transform the ideal of multilingualism into a reality;
- Secondly a practical one: it was found that students having mastered this level are able to follow most of the courses offered in the language of instruction;
- Thirdly an administrative and legal one: to clearly define a threshold necessary language wise to be eligible for the Campus Europae Certificate and/or Degree.

Language-wise Campus Europae students are not asked to master the language of their host country before their arrival - that would limit the number of students who would qualify for a period of studies abroad. In fact our students are highly encouraged not to disregard countries where minority languages are spoken. However, reaching B1 level competence in any language is not an easy task nor an equal task for all students. In order to facilitate it, a six-step structure has been put in place:

- Step 1: Students not familiar with the language of the host university or are in need of further training are advised to make an initial contact while still in the home country by using their home university's possibilities to learn a foreign language - Campus Europae students ideally begin

their contact with the language of the host university 6 months before the study period starts.

Even students with no prior knowledge of the host university's language of instruction should be able to reach A1 level, being ready to take on A2 level on arrival at the host institution. For all students, whose home university isn't prepared to offer the necessary courses or who cannot attend language classes due to other commitments or want to intensify or speed up their learning, step 2 is offered by Campus Europae.

- Step 2: Students are invited to register for an introductory online course via the Hook-Up! e-learning module offered by Campus Europae.¹¹

The Hook-Up! language learning gateway was launched in 2008 precisely to support language learning across the Campus Europae network, making the learning of the language of the host university central to the mobility experience and making this learning accessible to all. It also supports a new approach to the learning and teaching of the at that time twelve Campus Europae languages. Founded by the European Commission, through its Lifelong Learning Programme, Hook-Up! (<http://languagelearning.campuseuropae.org>) is

¹¹ languagelearning.campuseuropae.org

a collaborative teaching and learning platform which is part of a blended approach to language learning combining self study, interactive sessions supported online and face to face. After the end of the European funding Campus Europae continued offering this tool out of its own resources. Using Moodle, Hook-Up! offers the online learning material divided according to the levels of the "Common European Framework of Reference for Languages" (CEFRL) and an administrative support for the organisation of tutoring sessions at given times of the academic year delivered through Skype or Wiziq on an individual or group basis. It also functions as a repository for learning material for face to face courses for learners of the foreign language once they are already at the host university. Hook-Up!'s goal is to motivate students to language learning in a fun and meaningful way, while at the same time contributing to their mobility experience and academic success.

The Hook-Up! project has revealed its potential to enable mobility students throughout the network to effectively learn the language of the host institution, adding a new language to their multilingual repertory with immediate added value to their studies and long term added value to their professional competences. In addition the extension of Hook-Up! from 2011 allowed participating universities to offer online tuition to all its members in all the languages of the network at various levels of the CEFRL, thus con-

tributing greatly to the universities' capacity to teach languages and to the range of languages on offer. It thus functions as a facilitator of multilingualism at an institutional level, moving far beyond the boundaries of the mobility network itself. Thus, Campus Europae and the participating institutions work together in their commitment to providing language learning services to CE movers: both outgoing and incoming. In addition there are signs that the structure put in place by institutions for their CE movers has an influence on other language teaching structures which may be in place.

- Step 3: Students are required to participate during 4 – 6 weeks in the intensive courses offered for incoming students at the host university prior to the study period with 30 hours per week.

As not all member universities did offer such programmes, perhaps Campus Europae's most specific contribution to increasing language learning provision in the member universities has been the financing of the Intensive Language courses before the start of the academic year. Initially planned to provide a solid grounding in the host language over a period of 4 to 6 weeks, with 6 hours of tuition, 6 days a week, these intensive courses have adapted to time and financial constraints.

- Step 4: Students are encouraged to continue their language studies with ongoing tuition in the host language throughout the first, and if possible, during the second semester abroad.

During this study period in the host institution, the Hook-Up! platform combined with face-to-face tuition, acts as a constant support to learning as students progress through their mobility year. The listed steps are combined with other forms of support, namely in universities where few courses are available in English. The exact mix of tools varies across the network, with language courses often being combined with peer and/or tutor support, English bibliography and other accompanying measures. While such a large network accommodates considerable diversity with regards language learning strategies all are designed with a view to safeguard the student's capacity to perform normally from an academic viewpoint while being abroad.

With regards to final exams and examinations, most professors were found to be willing to arrange for either oral exams or accept written works in English, but this remains to be agreed in detail upon arrival.

But as students are very often quite reluctant to move out of their comfort zone and embark on the adventure of learning a new language provisions have been made to overcome this attitude. The most important is Campus Europae's policy of sending out

students for a whole academic year. This leads to a mental state of preparedness and willingness to immerse into a foreign language and culture, because the stay abroad is an extended one. Whereas it was noted that students knowing that they were only abroad for one semester (12-14 weeks), were tempted to try to survive with their Home language and English.

- Step 5: This changed attitude is backed up by another module developed by Campus Europae : the Learning Employability Placement (LEP).

This programme is giving students a chance to get to know the every day life of the host country outside the academic ivory tower by internships in study related work places, thus contributing considerably to the language immersion situation.

- Step 6: On return home, students continue to have access to Hook-Up! materials.

This allows them to maintain their contact with the language they have just learnt, with other learners and speakers of that language, and thus they are able to keep up and extend their competence after their study visit. Many of them find their way to the cultural institutes of their host countries at home, like the "Institut Francais", the Portuguese "Instituto Camões", the Spanish "Instituto Cervantes", and the German

“Goethe Institut” etc, thus deepening their understanding of the host county’s culture.

The example of Teacher Training and Education

The particular case of Teacher Training and Education, one of Campus Europae’s eight Subject Committees¹², will be the focus of the final part of this paper. Teacher training is usually considered to be a typically national affair, which does not give much attention to students with another language background. Thus, on the assumption that successful implementation of the programme in this field will be an indicator for likely success in the other fields as well, it was considered a worthwhile exercise to look more closely at how the language learning concept was working in this case.

The Sample

Since 2005, Campus Europae has been asking the exchange students after their 1st semester abroad and at the end of their stay about their impressions and the success of their studies. Since 2007 this survey has been carried out by means of an electronic ques-

tionnaire using “Survey Monkey”. The questionnaires offer about 30 questions (yes/no, multiple choice, open answers). Teacher training and education students form a large group in our sample: usually between 40 and 50% stated that they were studying to become teachers (although some of the students were actually from other study areas).

There are numerous training structures, models or ways of becoming a teacher in force across Europe¹³. Besides this structural variety, the organisation of the curriculum in teacher training programmes may vary¹⁴. This situation alone raises a specific and complex challenge for anybody who – as a future teacher – wants to study in more than one European country. The challenge is even more demanding, because teacher education is organized and regulated on a national basis, giving more importance to the fact that students master the national or regional language and curriculum, than that they should learn a foreign or foreign languages and be exposed to different curricula and ways of working. This is in spite of the current trends towards expanding European mobility, the growing diversification of

¹² Business administration and Economics, Engineering, Humanities, Law, Medicine, Natural Sciences, Social Sciences, Teacher Training and Education;

¹³ For example, we find one tier structures, where one programme leads to the professional qualification as a teacher, and two tier structures, where students first have to achieve a degree in an academic field other than education and afterwards study in teacher training institutions, where they are expected to sit another examination to be acknowledged as fully trained professionals. And there are also mixed structures.

¹⁴ For instance, the curriculum of teacher training may be subject-oriented or it may be aimed at qualifying teachers to work with specific age groups or in certain settings, like the teaching of children with special needs, vocational education or pre-academic qualification. On the other hand, university programmes may be focused on educational, methodological and didactical questions, or on specific teaching subjects, or they may aim to achieve a balance between the two. In this latter case, students gain an academic grounding in one or two fields of science or humanities and follow a parallel training in the field of education, methods and pedagogy.

social contexts due to intensified migration flows, and the varied nature of the European language landscape which is estimated to include some 220 languages¹⁵ not counting the wealth of the languages spoken in Europe by migrants. In fact, it is estimated that some 450 languages are spoken in Europe. It is our argument, therefore, that teacher training students face a particularly challenging situation regarding the challenges of mobility and language(s) acquisition.

The Language Situation

The awareness of the diverse linguistic situation and the individual knowledge of the language of the host country before going abroad are of course of great importance for the later success or failure. Therefore all outgoing students were asked, in how many foreign languages they were able to communicate. It is striking that only about 12% of future teachers, in contrast with 88% of students in other academic or professional fields, were among those who claimed not to know more than one foreign language. At the other end of the scale, of those claiming to know 5 languages, 87% were future teachers and only 13% belonged to other fields. Given the fact that according to the EU the average number of languages spoken by students in the EU-27 is 1.3¹⁶ languages, all Campus Europae students (teachers as well as non-teachers) represent

a special, highly prepared selection of the student body, with an average of 2.63 languages per student.

Looking at the number of languages the students known after the return from exchange, the programme is without doubt a success: the minimum number of languages teacher training students have mastered is 3, the maximum is 7, whereas other students in the programme have reported a minimum of 2 and a maximum of 5. The average number of languages for Teacher Training students equals 4.1, and for the other students in the Campus Europae programme 3.4. Therefore it is no surprise that 83% of all our participants state their satisfaction or even great satisfaction with the stay abroad with relation to the acquisition of a new language (10% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 5% dissatisfied, and 2% very dissatisfied). For the subgroup of Teacher Training students, the satisfaction is even higher, with 37% being very satisfied and 53% satisfied, compared to Non Teacher Training students with 41% and 38% respectively.

The Academic Situation

Success in language learning is only one element of understanding European unity and diversity by studying abroad. If in spite of the various traditions the mastering of the new language would enable the students

¹⁵ Lewis, 2009

¹⁶ On ISCED level 3. ~ Cf. <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&pcode=tps00056&plugin=1>

to achieve academic success this would be even more important. Therefore, it was essential for us to address the relationship between learning the language of the host country and academic success. Above all, since it can be argued that the task of learning a new language can contribute to academic success, but equally that it could turn out to be an obstacle! We therefore asked the students after their exchange period: "Is it possible to study successfully in a difficult language setting even in the complex structures of teacher training, to acquire not only a new language but to gain insight in knowledge useful for the future professional work in the home country? "

Encouragingly, the overall answer given by the students was a clear "yes". 100% of those who considered their academic success as "Excellent" or "Good" rated language as important. It is interesting that of all those who rate the language influence not only as "important" but as "very important", 68% attribute their good academic success to language knowledge and 32% their poor achievement.

In order to identify areas for which the command of a foreign language equivalent to B1 turned out to be an asset in the attempt to study successfully, and areas, for which even mastering the language (C1 or C2) has not been of great help, we encouraged our students to give, in the form of open text answers, comments on why they appreci-

ated the programme, on reasons for problems and to give recommendations. Most of the students who made the effort to give remarks were those satisfied or very satisfied with their exchange. In answer to the questions: "What did you appreciate most?" "Which serious problems did you have to face?" students answered with respect to

- their academic success,
- the development of their personality
- their linguistic achievement .

Some examples for a positive or negative influence of language knowledge may illustrate the linguistic category of importance in the context of this paper.¹⁷

Positive:

- My academic progress suffered a little bit..., but it was worth it - now I speak Portuguese fluently and in the second semester everything was far more easier already
- Intensive language tutoring and learning opportunities
- I loved studying in a foreign language, there was so much more to discover

Negative:

- Writing exams and term papers on a new foreign language
- Not being able to express my thoughts exactly in a foreign language
- It is a pity that the academic progress

¹⁷ The remarks are given in the students' original spelling and grammar.

suffers a little bit, but it is ok for whom likes languages

- The most serious problem in the beginning is language barrier, because, I didn't used to study on foreign languages.
- The beginning when I didn't speak the language at all
- Studying and passing exams in two different languages.

Campus Europae – a pluricentric, multilingual campus

With a view to assessing the potential of the Campus Europae approach to forming a new type of multilingual university making use of campuses in a multitude of linguistic settings, we carried out a preliminary SWOT analysis which produced interesting results in five different dimensions: faculty, study structure, language, students as plurilingual individuals, and the Lisbon process of bringing together study and work place experience. In the context of this paper the following findings are of importance:

Strengths: The language policy is a clear strength and the language learning platform, Hook-Up!, as described above, can be seen as the necessary link between language courses at the home university and classes for incoming students at the host university. The overwhelming interest of the Campus Europae students to maintain or to further develop the competence in the language acquired at the host university

– even if this language is not needed for academic success at home - proves the success of this approach to develop plurilingual individuals and to trigger an awareness of the advantage of the European unity in diversity.

The network's model to combine international study experience with workplace experience, the Learning Employability Placement Programme (LEP), is considered to be an important step towards allowing a wider access to the programme and for qualifying students for a European citizenship.

Weaknesses: The restricted number of languages offered in most of the universities and the limited percentage of room for electives (like language) in many BA/MA programmes

Opportunities: They certainly include the growing priority attributed to internationalisation in higher education institutions, and the orientation towards achieving excellence of universities, particularly in this case with regard to the establishment of language policies, the interest of universities in distance education and the growing tendency of universities to work together with companies.

Threats: The tendency to adopt English as the language of international communication in higher education as well as in professional contexts is motivating more and

more students to study this language and consider other languages as irrelevant.

Concluding remarks

It is clear to us that Campus Europae and the importance it attributes to the attainment of language competences, both on account of the advantages of this for individuals and for European citizenship, make a positive contribution to the establishment of multilingualism as a competence and as a value in individuals, in institutions and in society (European Commission, 2007). Students who participate in this programme can attain B1 level skills in two languages, other than the ones they already know, which may be amongst the lesser taught languages, thus acting as an added-value to their professional portfolio and an added-value to European linguistic diversity. It has been observed that impacts are felt within the institutions which participate in Campus Europae. Their student mobility rates rise and diversify, more and different languages are spoken, taught and learnt, and strategies are found for dealing with the increasing diversity and bureaucratic systems are adjusted. Bottom-up processes of change develop which play their part in the transformation of Europe's institutions towards a multilingual / multicultural paradigm. From a social point of view, the increasing multilingualism and intercultural skills gained by Campus Europeans will

have a crucial role to play in the establishment of social and economic well-being in more inclusive and more just societies.

Birgit Brödermann

Intercultural Consultant,
Project Coordinator,
Arbeit und Leben
Hamburg

*"Member universities
had a new European
idol in mind:
combining academic
qualification with
international
employability and an
awareness of European
identity"*

Bologna meets Lisbon

Studying and working is a reality which roughly half of the European students is well familiar with, and that leaves many structurally excluded from engaging in a meaningful exchange experience; CE was in the forefront of finding ways to bridge the gap between academia, companies and NGOs in such a way that it strengthened the learning experience of the students involved and enabled them to support themselves during a year abroad.

When in 2003 the Campus Europaen University Foundation - Campus Europae started its cooperation, all 19 member universities had a new European idol in mind: "combining academic qualification with international employability and an awareness of European identity".

This challenging idea would meet exactly the expectations of both the Bologna Declaration of 1999 that prioritized Universities as one of the primary instruments in assisting new

academics and graduates in European Employability and the Lisbon Strategy from March 2000 that primarily required a "knowledge based economy".

Remained the question by which steps this special job opportunity, tailor-made and study-related, could be offered to the students during their study year abroad.

Since 2003 the Hamburg University cooperation partner Arbeit und Leben Hamburg, a major further education provider in Hamburg, has been in charge of finding those particular "Learning Employability Places" (LEP). These LEPs, providing a combination of studying and working on an eight to ten hours weekly basis, have become one of the most distinguishing characteristics of the Campus Europea programme.

While being for the majority of the students a remarkable success story, achieving a relevant LEP still represents a real challenge for each of them. From

my personal experience I can say, that the more the students are prepared for this intercultural adventure the better the outcomes are. Hence, the other way round, it is quite unlikely that the students are reaching their own goals if not appropriately prepared.

The reasons for this are manifold. Committing oneself for a long-term placement on top of the academic studies at University is a demanding process in terms of jumping language barriers on one side and trying to get along with unfamiliar company and working structures in the host country on the other side.

Besides, the language of the host country is again divided in everyday language among students, academic language at University (though a lot of lectures are held in English) and a business related language during the internship.

Moreover, the students may become confronted with never yet experienced requirements, e.g. not being allowed to constantly use their mobile phones during working hours or being obliged to make a difference between themselves and their boss.

Some of the students may have already made experiences in the professional life, others not. They are entitled to become – in many cases for the first time in their lives – an “apprentice” with manners and present

at all times. One is tempted to describe this cultural clash as: “Young student’s informal modern life behaviour” meets “open minded formal employer’s expectations”.

Reading the reports of the students this work – study balance is being underpinned in such a way that they have been making an enormous effort in improving their personality while learning the unknown language, becoming familiar with the new culture of their environment and in making the best out of their LEP – experiences in relation to their studies and later employability. (The latter aspect is also subject to discussion for both the students and the employers at place due to the inevitable language lack.)

Irina Baigozina from Russia underwent an eight months LEP at the “Museum of Work” in Hamburg where she was dealing with database materials, filing documents and digitalizing print media. She learnt how to work with specific computer programs and how to do internet archiving: *“It is my first work experience and I am very happy to practice in such a wonderful place, which gives me a lot of opportunities in the future. Due to this LEP, I could get acquainted with German working system, attained inestimable working skills, which are so necessary for my curriculum vitae and in everyday life, enhance my level of German language and meet admirable people.”*

Taiija Müllärinnen from Finland did two LEPs, one from September 2011 until the end of February 2012 in the “CVJM Kindertagesheim” in Hamburg and the other one from April 2012 to middle June 2012 in the Heinrich- Wolgast-Schule.

Taiija could practice and improve her German remarkably well by speaking with the children and listening to their feedback. She was respected by the staff and also well seen by the parents. During her time at primary school she was mostly observing, taking part in a project and being in permanent contact with other teachers and school helpers. One of her particular interests lied in the area of comparing the Finnish and the German school system: *"In conclusion I can say that my LEP-practices were very useful for me and most probably valuable in the future. I learned a lot about myself and at the same time about my coming work with children!"*

Sandra Garcia Pérez from Spain did a nine months placement at the music department of the “International School of Hamburg”. She was mainly observing in the elementary classes and the six primary classes. Here she learnt how to implement different educational resources such as games, images, videos, colors, songs and shapes into the teaching. Throughout the two terms she could see the evolution of the pupils as well as their different attitudes towards the

course. She also learnt by a great variety of didactical musical arrangements many techniques to prepare classes and how to direct them. Besides, she took the opportunity to talk to the teachers about the differences of public and private schools in Germany.

"In general I have been really pleased with school's responsible, teachers and the entire organization of the classes I have attended because I feel that I have learned a lot, both in English and music didactic, and that I can take a lot of advantage of this year of practice at the school."

These three by way of example chosen CE - students have been performing greatly throughout the entire time of their stay abroad. On the whole, they are perfectly illustrating the whole range of a meaningful combination of studying and undertaking a study-related working opportunity. Having been the Hamburg Campus Europae LEP - finder and coordinator for about five years now, I come to the conclusion that in the end an amalgam of at least three key factors such as a high level of motivation, self-reflection and ambition from the student's side combined with an excellent orientation and guidance from the coordinator's side are being the prerequisite for a fruitful LEP.

Fuada Stankovic

Rector,
University of Novi Sad
2001 - 2004

"universities always
had and still have a
unique role to promote
universal human
values through
universal university
culture"

Tearing down borders in Higher Education

CE has members universities hailing from Serbia, Russia and Belarus. Is this an important contribution for such partners, in terms involving them in the practical implementation of the Bologna process? And in what ways working closely with partners that are not active in Erasmus enriches such a network and their students?

University of Novi Sad (UNS) entered Campus Europae in 2003 and started exchanging students from 2004/2005. It was a first European mobility programme that opened its doors fully to a non-EU university, from Serbia. In 2008, UNS was offered to join Erasmus Mundus Action 2. Serbia becomes eligible for more international mobility schemes with regards to "Erasmus for All", the new programme proposed by the EU Commission for Education, Training, Youth and Sport due to start in 2014.

CE has been much more to the UNS than just one of the mobility schemes.

Being the Rector when UNS

was invited to join CE, I was delighted with this offer and still believe that it is a wonderful project. But escaping to be too subjective I asked our International office to sum up results based on the ten years of experience and here is their opinion:

(1) CE brought professors into regular contact and established links between related fields. It has built up TRUST. It has brought students together – promoting CE on initiatives such as Tour d'Europe, regular meetings of student council, etc. It has showed to UNS students that they are not only good enough for academic success, but that their creativity is appreciated and valued in a European network of universities;

(2) The Programme taught participants about challenges of the practical implementation of Bologna. It was the first time use of tools such as learning agreement, transcript of records... and most importantly

the issue of academic recognition of study periods abroad;

(3) Participants from UNS felt honoured to have been treated equally with all other partners and their results from the very start showed that they were ready and able to support the main concepts of the CE programme – from the language learning and provision, to the introduction of more fields of study in the exchange scheme;

(4) CE has been active every year, despite financial obstacles. It has become a brand name at the University and it now involves many academics, researchers, scholars, students and staff, who know its philosophy and who make sure that the quality of student exchange is raised every year;

(5) The importance of mobility through CE was recognized by the Provincial government which is giving scholarships to the best students who apply for exchange programme within CE.

CE started in the period when it became obvious that large changes were approaching the world of knowledge. At the beginning of the 21st century there are various policy discourses on the new role of knowledge and learning, workplace setting, external influences that people and organisations are increasingly exposed to. Influence of paradigms for growth, development and

particular types of skills is recognized globally, interpersonal skills which support people in their understanding and the cooperation with others, especially.

Every group, region, country, also have different set of values, personal and social. The issue of belonging to your own group, but also to a wider community and to the world is becoming very important in the globalised world.

It is so with sharing of European values and belonging to the European culture. Universities always had and still have a unique role to promote universal human values through universal university culture. For that, internationalization, promoting and advancing the university's international cooperation is the natural characteristics of every university. It was so with the oldest European universities and it so today.

Campus Europae is one of the great projects contributing to the mutual understanding of young people throughout Europe, which is showing in practice how European culture exists in its very part, from the West to the East, from the North to the South, independently from specific values and habits within each region. CE contributed very much to the recognition in the Eastern and Central Europe that their nations share common European values. The striving of CE to combine academic qualifications with an awareness of EU identity was confirmed

very much in the last decade.

One of the curiosities when looking to the structure of incoming students to the UNS is that the largest number of them were coming from Portugal. This country is relatively far from Serbia but the students from both countries found that they had very much in common. One of the results is that Portuguese language became popular in Novi Sad and the University in cooperation with the Embassy of Portugal organizes open language courses for students and staff.

Stimulating exchange students to learn language of a country where they were going for a year of study is one of the great and unique features of the Campus Europae project. It is well known that within Erasmus students are mostly choosing the large countries where the major foreign languages are spoken. Within CE, students learn languages which are less spoken and contribute better understanding and communication among different cultures within Europe. Recently, at the University Novi Sad (Faculty of Philosophy) a new Centre for Serbian as a foreign language is established and incoming CE students are obliged to acquire B1 certificate.

With the growing number of mobility programmes and mobile students and staff both to and from the UNS – the process of internationalization began to permeate various services both at the faculty level from

the accounting offices to the technical support units and language centres to various academic departments requiring again benchmarks and quality measures from the central university level.

University is mobilizing the appropriate resources from its constitutional parts for the better coordination and promotion of incoming and outgoing mobility and academic needs of foreign students and scholars.

First University led Buddy-network was established to support foreign students and scholars, crossing the borders between disciplines and faculties. Academic needs of foreign students started to affect academic provision through the efforts of a number of academic staff to provide consultations, literature and exams in English.

University of Novi Sad mission and vision cover advancement of quality and excellence in knowledge, research and art, social responsibility and accountability, democracy and equal educational opportunities to all stakeholders, respect for human rights, respect for education roots and tradition, development and innovation, internationalization, common European values advanced through the Bologna process.

In the coming years Serbia is becoming eligible for more international mobility schemes, its universities are taking stock of their internationalization processes and

implementation of Bologna related reforms against the background of ambitious goals set in the new Serbian Educational Strategy (2012). In the past decade many developments happened to support this ambition such as new interdisciplinary programmes in English, growing number and quality of administrative staff, new services for academics and students. Project Campus Europae stimulated and supported very much these developments.

was strong stimulus for university reforms. The idea of removal or reduction of obstacles for the free movement of students, teachers and researchers across Europe and establishment of sufficiently common elements that can enable comparison and recognition of certifications for work across the EU was widely recognized within Serbian academic community and more and more supported by the governments at all levels.

The benefits of increased student and staff mobility for the higher education system in Serbia were numerous. The most important

Sjur Bergan

Head of the Education
Department
Council of Europe

*"That cannot be but
a society built on a
culture of democracy
and human rights,
and such a culture
cannot be built and
sustained unless
higher education rises
to the challenge"*

Putting Human Rights and Higher Education on the Agenda

A seemingly simple title like "Putting Human Rights and Higher Education on the Agenda" raises more questions than can reasonably be answered in a brief article. Here I will try to answer three of them: "what?", "on whose agenda?", and "how?" as well as consider briefly education as a right. I will close by a brief reflection on the role of the Luxembourg Forum.

What is Human Rights?

Human rights are a core European value. Even if European countries do not always act accordingly – and for this very reason are sometimes condemned by the European Court of Human Rights – it is difficult to imagine someone taking a principled stand against human rights and still be counted as European. By way of illustration, the actions of the Lukashenka regime in Belarus have been sufficient for it to be considered a European pariah, with a number of higher education leaders among the

Belarusians on the EU black list. This is not to say that "everything" is human rights. Therefore, it may be useful to remind ourselves that human rights have been codified through the European Convention on Human Rights as well as through Protocols to it – and at global level through the Universal Declaration on Human Rights. This is what should be taught and what should be used as the basis for reflection on human rights. The latter is important, education is not only about learning facts but also about developing the ability to reason, to analyze and to apply knowledge and understanding critically and in new circumstances. Only in this way will a knowledge and understanding of the legal texts be transformed into a culture of human rights, that is a set of attitudes and behaviors consistent with Europe's human rights values (Council of Europe 2010).

On Whose agenda?

The easy answer is that human rights should be on everyone's agenda. However, this is not an immediately operational statement: if everyone is concerned, nobody takes responsibility. For higher education to play an important role in promoting a culture of human rights, institutional leaders and higher education policy makers need to identify with the democratic mission of higher education. This is a major challenge, because democracy and human rights are low on the practical agenda of European higher education leaders.

The Council of Europe has identified four major purposes for higher education:

- Preparation for sustainable employment;
- Preparation for life as active citizens in democratic societies
- Personal development
- The development and maintenance, through teaching, learning and research, of a broad, advanced knowledge base (Bergan 2005, Council of Europe 2007).

However, public discourse on education in Europe today could easily mislead the casual observer to conclude that education has a single purpose: to contribute to economic growth. In this, European higher education leaders are markedly more narrow

minded than their US peers, who strongly underline the civic mission of higher education while also recognizing its economic importance. Tellingly, in the four conferences on the democratic mission of higher education that the Council of Europe has organized jointly with the US Steering Committee of the International Consortium for Higher Education, Civic Responsibility and Democracy¹, US university and college presidents have participated in droves, whereas European participants have too often been academics with an agenda but without commensurate institutional responsibilities.

European rectors, deans and ministerial policy makers must make the democratic and human rights mission a part of their higher education agenda.

How?

Some students undoubtedly both need and are offered specially tailored courses in human rights. Lawyers with insufficient understanding of the European Convention of Human Rights and of the Human Rights Court would be inadequately trained for their profession (Council of Europe 2004), and the same case can easily be made for political scientists with insufficient understanding of the role of human rights in international relations as well as in national politics and society.

However, the need for an understanding of

¹ <http://www.internationalconsortium.org/>

human rights is not limited to specialists and the understanding is not necessarily best developed through mandatory courses. Many of the Council of Europe's member states had experience with mandatory political education in a previous system and are rightly skeptical of the idea even if the purpose today would be worthy. Higher education institutions must provide students of all background and disciplines with a learning environment that helps develop a culture of democracy and human rights through daily practice and not as something to be studied only an hour or two a week and forgotten for the rest.

Higher education as a right?

The right to education is a part of the Human Rights Convention as well as the case law of the Court but the provisions address mandatory rather than higher education. This is perhaps partly a reflection of the fact that the advent of mass higher education is more recent than at least the Convention itself, even if some of its protocols are of newer date. Our understanding of rights evolves with our societies but at the same time, national authorities are reluctant to take on additional legal obligations in times of economic crisis.

The Council of Europe has in recent years developed three standard setting texts on the responsibility of public authorities for higher education. The Recommendation on public responsibility already referred to

(Council of Europe 2007) takes as its starting point the declaration by European ministers, repeated twice (Bologna Process 2001 and 2003) that higher education is a "public good and a public responsibility". In order to make this declaration operational, the Recommendation establishes different levels of public responsibility for different aspects of higher education. Thus, public authorities have exclusive responsibility for establishing the framework within which higher education is provided; leading responsibility for ensuring effective equal opportunities to higher education for all citizens, as well as ensuring that basic research remains a public good; and substantial – but hence not exclusive - responsibility for financing higher education and research, the provision of higher education and research, as well as for stimulating and facilitating financing and provision by other sources within the framework developed by public authorities.

The second recommendation (Council of Europe 2012 a) addresses the public responsibility for academic freedom and institutional autonomy, both of which are cornerstones of democratic societies, while the third (Council of Europe 2012 b) focuses on ensuring quality education, again with an emphasis on public responsibility. This recommendation is perhaps particularly important because even if excellence is one of the main goals of today's education policies, our understanding of quality is rarely discussed or made explicit. The recommen-

dition links the notion of quality to the multiple purposes of education and combines a holistic view of quality education with linking measures and the ways in public responsibility should be exercised to consideration of inter alia the level of education and the age and autonomy of students, compulsory vs. non-compulsory education and general measures vs. measures for vulnerable groups.

The Luxembourg Forum

Campus Europae renders European higher education great service by organizing a forum on its role in furthering a culture of human rights. By gathering decision makers and practitioners from the academic community as well as from public authorities the Luxembourg Forum has the potential to help set a human rights agenda for higher edu-

cation in Europe. The Luxembourg Forum should help broaden our horizons beyond what is immediately useful to encompass also what is important in the longer run, from the economy to the society of which both the economy and the higher education community are a part and which they should serve, and to help define and reimagine not only what we produce but who we are as Europeans in the 21st century. It is an endeavor that the Council of Europe is happy to join and that should be guided by Eugenio Tironi's assertion that the kind of education we need should be guided by the kind of society we want (Tironi 2005). That cannot be but a society built on a culture of democracy and human rights, and such a culture cannot be built and sustained unless higher education rises to the challenge.

Luxembourg Forum on Human Rights and Higher Education

Under the auspices of

Organised by

In cooperation with

Supported by

Mr. François Biltgen

Minister for Higher
Education and Research
Luxembourg

"A thousand students have turned the initial idea into a living reality. Their continued enthusiasm for Campus Europae has made of them the perfect ambassadors not only for Campus Europae itself, but also for the very idea of European citizenship"

On the way to the 20th anniversary of Campus Europae

Ten years of Campus Europae – a short span of time, yet time enough for those who have shaped Campus Europae to write history.

When towards the end of the 1990ies, the idea of Campus Europae first originated student mobility did not need to be invented; after all, the Erasmus programme was well underway and had already become a household name within academia. Yet, Campus Europae set out to reinvent student mobility by first of all arguing that for mobility to have an effect it needed a longer stay abroad and an experience of more than one country. The very concept of student mobility was thus rooted in the concept of European citizenship – the young generation should be Europeans before being nationals.

In the course of those ten years, Campus Europae has also transcended the notion that Europe only means the Europe

of the 27 Member States. The partner universities testify to the fact that there is a European culture and understanding that is wider than political boundaries.

Campus Europae has challenged traditional ways of learning; it has asked the partner universities to forego their well - established concepts of curricula so that the mobile student can fully benefit from his stay abroad, it has asked them to go new ways in the language preparation and in the acquisition of language skills so that multiculturalism and multilingualism meet and it has asked them to explore ways for work placements at a time when the world of work and the world of academia tended to go separate ways.

Campus Europae has thus managed to anchor its concept firmly in the European tradition of the wandering student while at the same time exploring new ways and being at

the forefront of new developments in higher education. Therefore, the proponents of the project combined foresight and wisdom and the universities showed the necessary courage to engage in this project.

A thousand students have turned the initial idea into a living reality. Their continued enthusiasm for Campus Europae has made of them the perfect ambassadors not only for Campus Europae itself, but also for the very idea of European citizenship.

To all who have contributed to Campus Europae a great thank you!

Prof. Christoph
Ehmann

Secretary-General
EUF-CE

"The important role students play in giving student exchange a "normal" place in their lives, led to the constitution of the Campus Europae Student Council. The Student Council, consisting of student representatives of each member universities, is an integral part of the Campus Europae network"

History

Campus Europae started as a project, based on a proposal of former German Chancellor Helmut Kohl, who wanted to give a new impulse to education in the European Union during the German presidency in the first half of 1999.

A group of German experts in higher education (chairs: Dr. Konrad Schily, former President of the private University of Witten, and Prof. Meinulf Dierkes, former President of the Social Science Research Centre Berlin) were asked to design a concept, which would give a "European dimension" to higher education. However, the events in Kosovo during 1999 led to other political priorities being placed on the agenda within the European Union, with the result that in early 2000 the government of the Grand Duchy was asked to assume patronage of the project. In May 2000, Prime Minister Juncker announced the initiative as an official Luxembourg project during his inaugural speech. A memorandum, prepared by

Dr. Schily, Prof. Dierkes, former Senator Christa Thoben, Managing Director of the Bucerius Law School Hamburg Jürgen Bühring, former Undersecretary Dr. Christoph Ehmann, and former director of Deutsche Bank Luxembourg, Dr. Ekkehard Stork, was distributed in early 2000. It recommended the creation of a university association: "Campus Europae". It substantiated the concept of a close integration of European university systems, a process initiated in 1999 by European education ministers within the framework of the Bologna process. This memorandum described in detail the steps towards a co-operation between universities in the network, the changes to be achieved, together with the procedures for the implementation of the project.

Under the patronage of Prime Minister Jean Claude Juncker and Science Minister Erna Hennicot-Schoepges, the project was launched with a conference on 20/21 June 2001 in Luxembourg which was attend-

ed both by representatives from governments as well as universities. This launching conference resulted in a significant change of perspective of crucial importance. The original idea was that both governments and universities would jointly work towards the development of Campus Europae. Yet, the discussion at the conference showed that this route was blocked by a multitude of formal and ideological obstacles. Nevertheless, the universities in attendance decided to undertake the project fully exploiting their own decision-making autonomy.

The universities willing to undertake further cooperation agreed on the following closing communiqué:

"The university representatives agree to examine the establishment of a consortium consisting of universities committed to excellence in research and learning. Therefore, the university representatives agree to consider and to examine the establishment of the European University Foundation as an organizational platform for the cooperating universities. The European University Foundation will be the coordinating framework; it serves to create conditions that are necessary for the successful cooperation between the member universities; this framework contributes to greater self-governance and a strategic vision. The main purpose of the consortium is to create a field of experimentation generating exemplary experiences,

which would then feed into the process of establishing a network of higher education in Europe. The consortium mainly aims at allowing students to gather multi-various experiences in at least two participating universities in two different countries as well as to efficiently pursue their studies. This should ultimately lead to the creation of a Campus Europae (CE) label. Close cooperation and effective coordination between universities is thus required."

The participating universities therefore decided to form the association with the interested universities, to fully exploit their own decision-making possibilities and to include governments only in isolated cases.

This included the attempt, at least during the planning phase, to steer clear of direct state finance as much as possible. Between 1998 and 2003, Campus Europae was funded by resources of the Quandt Foundation, the Allianz Kulturstiftung, the Volkswagen Foundation and a grant by the media entrepreneur, Leo Kirch. The government of the Grand Duchy of Luxemburg hosted all the conferences before it took over the financing of Campus Europae in 2004, time at which it provided the present secretariat of Campus Europae with a venue in the Château de Munsbach, close to the capital of the Grand Duchy.

Following the 2001 launching conference,

seven expert groups gathering professors from all participating universities undertook pilot projects in the areas of humanities, natural sciences, teacher training, medicine, business, law and engineering. The main objective of these working groups was to investigate in which way mobility solutions could be developed to systematically foster student exchange across the network.

Academic cooperation quickly became the heart and soul of Campus Europae and over time the workgroups developed into the CE Subject Committees, which are until today the organ which provides the framework for intensive academic cooperation and is charged with setting up ex-ante recognition mechanisms.

At the end of 2003, the Rectors' Council elected the first President and Secretary General, respectively Prof. Noel Whelan and Prof. Christoph Ehmann. Prof. Noel Whelan succeeded outgoing President Dr Konrad Schily, who is one of the founders of Campus Europae and one of the main driving forces having overseen the critical period of its establishment.

The year 2004 was poised to be a pivotal year for Campus Europae. Alongside with the first experimental student exchanges, the definitive installation of the Secretariat of Campus Europae in the Grand Duchy of Luxemburg was completed – a most ade-

quate venue due to the country's multicultural and multi-linguistic long-established tradition.

In the same year, the important role students play in giving student exchange a "normal" place in their lives, led to the constitution of the Campus Europae Student Council. The Student Council, consisting of student representatives of each member universities, is an integral part of the Campus Europae network.

Prof. Noel Whelan's four-year long mandate attained remarkable successes in consolidating and strengthening the network which grew from 11 to 18 member universities and launched its first 13 joint study programmes which have been brought to fruition to an excess of about 300 students. During his presidency, the additional CE projects: "Bologna meets Lisbon" which combines studying and working whilst abroad; the "CE-Bursary" offering a possibility for financing the "second year" as well as the outline of a "Campus Europae Degree" were developed.

In October 2007, Prof. Whelan was succeeded by Prof. Estela Pereira. In December 2007, the constitution of the European University Foundation – Campus Europae was signed by the member universities and came into force on the 28th of January 2008 by decree of the Grand Duke of Luxemburg, Henri.

References

Campus Europae (2003). Concept Campus Europae.
Luxembourg: Campus Europae.

Chambers, A. (2003). Language policy in higher education in Europe: a pilot survey. http://userpage.fu-berlin.de/%7Eenlu/downloads/language_policy_in_higher_education_in_Europe/July2003.doc. Accessed 10.06.2011.

Coleman, J. (2004) New contexts for university languages: the Bologna Process, globalisation and employability.
<http://www.lang.ltsn.ac.uk/resources/paper.aspx?resourceid=2255> Accessed 09.05.2006.

Council of Europe (2001) Common European Framework of Reference for Languages.
Cambridge: CUP.

European Commission Communication (2003) "The Role of the universities in the Europe of knowledge".
Brussels, European Commission. COM(2003) 58 final of 05.02.2003.

European Commission, Communication (2005) "A New Framework Strategy for Multilingualism".
Brussels, European Commission COM(2005) 596 final of 22.11.2005.

European Commission (2006) Special Eurobarometer 243 "Europeans and their Languages".
http://www.ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/archives/ebs/ebs_243_sum_en.pdf Accessed 10.06.2011.

European Commission (2007) High Level Group on Multilingualism.
Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.

European Commission (2009). GREEN PAPER Promoting the learning mobility of young people.
Brussels, COM(2009) 329 final

European Council Presidency Conclusions, Lisbon, 2000.
http://www.bologna-berlin2003.de/pdf/PRESIDENCY_CONCLUSIONS_Lissabon.pdf. Accessed 29.07.2011

Hartmann, Wilfried (1993). Vom isolierten Muttersprachunterricht zum Muttersprachunterricht in mehrsprachigen Gesellschaften. Erläuterungen zu sechs Thesen.
In: Pädagogik und Schule in Ost und West. 41. 1993. Heft 1. p. 12 - 20

Knight, J. (2003). Internationalization of higher education practices and priorities: 2003 IAU survey report. Paris: International Association of Universities

Lewis, M.P. Ed. (2009). Ethnologue: Languages of the World, 16th Edition. Dallas, Tex. SIL International. Online version: <http://www.ethnologue.com/>.

Moreira, G.(2007). Languages for Life or Long-life Languages? Towards a policy for languages in Higher Education. In HOWCROFT, Susan (coord.)
Actas do Encontro Internacional de Linguística Aplicada. Aveiro: Universidade de Aveiro, 2007. pp. 275-286. ISBN 978-972-789-226-6.

OECD (2005) The Definition and Selection of Key Competencies.
<https://www.pisa.oecd.org/dataoecd/47/61/35070367.pdf>. Accessed 10.06.2011.

Phillipson, R. Additive university multilingualism in English-dominant empire: the language policy challenges.
Luxembourg, 2010.

Tomasi, L. (2006) "Multilingualism: The Repercussions of EU Language Policies on Higher Education". How to achieve Multilingualism in Higher Education.
Proceedings of the EUF-CE Seminar on Language Learning held on 17th and 18th November 2005. Luxembourg 2006. Pp. 18 – 26.

Schröder, K. (2006) "Diversity of Languages – Knowledge of Foreign Languages and Cultural Tolerance as Prerequisites for European Integration". How to Achieve Multilingualism in Higher Education.
Proceedings of the EUF-CE Seminar on Language Learning held on 17th and 18th November 2005. Luxembourg 2006.

Tudor, I. The Challenge of the Bologna Process for Higher Education Language Teaching in Europe.

userpage.fu-berlin.de/~enlu/downloads/Bologna_ENLU_OK.rtf. Accessed 29.07.2011

Vogel, T. (2001) "Internationalization, Interculturality, and the Role of Foreign Languages in Higher Education".

Higher Education in Europe. Vol. XXVI.No.3 pp. 381- 389.

Bergan, Sjur (2005): "Higher Education as a "Public Good and a Public Responsibility": What Does it Mean?",

in Luc Weber and Sjur Bergan (eds.): The Public Responsibility for Higher Education and Research Strasbourg: Council of Europe Publishing Council of Europe Higher Education Series No. 2

Bologna Process (2001): Prague Communiqué.

Bologna Process (2003), Berlin Communiqué, "Realising the European Higher Education Area"

Adopted by European ministers of education on 19 September 2003.

Council of Europe (2004): Recommendation Rec(2004)4 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the European Convention on Human Rights in university education and professional training

Council of Europe (2007): Recommendation Rec(2007)6 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the public responsibility for higher education and research.

Council of Europe (2010): Recommendation Rec(2010)7 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the Council of Europe Charter on Education for Democratic Citizenship and Human Rights Education

Council of Europe (2012 a): Recommendation Rec(2012)7 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the responsibility of public authorities for academic freedom and institutional autonomy

Council of Europe (2012 b): Recommendation Rec(2012)13 of the Committee of Ministers

to member states on ensuring quality education

Tironi, Eugenio (2005): *El sueño chileno: comunidad, familia y nación en el Bicentenario* [The Chilean Dream: Community, Family and Nation at the Bicentenary], Taurus, Santiago de Chile.